

Evidence-Based Toxicology Manuscript Assessment Form

Editorial Triage of Stage One Submissions

Version 1.0.0 | 8 February 2023

This form is for study protocols.

Note for submitting authors: The overall EBT submission assessment process is concerned with the potential publishability of a Working Paper, i.e. the extent to which sufficient work has been done that the relevant community would consider it to be a unit of contribution to the scientific literature.

The first stage of assessment is Editorial Triage. The goal of this stage is to assess a Working Paper against a minimum set of standards relating to the utility, validity, and transparency of the work. The assessment includes checks on ethics, data availability, and other requirements relating to reuse of data generated by the study. The Editor may also comment on issues that they believe would be useful to address prior to peer-review.

Instructions for Editor: Please work through the triage questionnaire, then in the Summary Section provide a brief summary of the Working Paper, your overall impression of it in terms of compliance with the journal's expectations for manuscripts of its type, and answer the two questions in the compliance issues table.

Manuscript title	Protocol for designing INVITES-IN, a tool for assessing the internal validity of <i>in vitro</i> studies
Manuscript ID	TEBT-2023-0002
Handling Editor	Olwenn Martin
Editor ORCID	https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2724-7882

Triage Checks

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	1. Objectives, context, and mode of research				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Clarity about the knowledge goals or hypotheses of the research (e.g. PECO) <input type="checkbox"/> Justification for conducting the research (context, rationale) <input type="checkbox"/> Differentiation between research in confirmatory or exploratory mode <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please explain in comments)				
Comments	The context and rationale for conducting the research are clear and sound. This protocol has divided the project into three phases or studies. The formulation of objectives focuses on the stage of development of the proposed tools and knowledge goals are mentioned or implied but could potentially be expressed more explicitly.				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	2. Soundness and rigour of planned experimental approach				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Theory as to how the study delivers the knowledge goal <input type="checkbox"/> Planned identification and authentication of study components, if applicable <input type="checkbox"/> Planned approach to power and replicates <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plan for bias controls (randomisation, masking, calibration, training, etc.) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please explain in comments)				
Comments	<p>While the general framework of Whiting et al (2017) is given to justify the approach, the manuscript would benefit from developing discussions about current approaches to RoB tool development, consensus around best approach and the strength and limitations of the approach adopted.</p> <p>The experimental approach is well described and detailed. As with all focus group and Delphi-based methods, the selection of participant is critical in limiting potential bias. A list of criteria for representativeness of the study is given. What is currently missing is a more detailed description of methods to identify (nomination by project group may introduce bias) participants as well as method to verify the representativeness of the selected experts and address potential selection bias if detected by previous. Additionally, a process to consider potential conflicts of interests of participants is not currently detailed in the manuscript.</p>				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	3. Plan for the analysis of data and reporting of results				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Planned data normalisation and cleansing techniques <input type="checkbox"/> Planned analysis pipeline (qualitative, narrative, and/or statistical methods) <input type="checkbox"/> Planned summarisation and visualisation of results <input type="checkbox"/> Selectivity in use of data or emphasis on study results <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Other (please explain in comments)				
Comments	<p>The plan for analysis is clear and detailed. The plans for reporting are less clear (see Domain 4).</p>				

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	4. Transparency and reproducibility				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input type="checkbox"/> Citation of data, program code, and methods (TOP 1 - L3) <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Plans for provision of code, data, and materials (TOP 2,3,4 - L2)				

	<input type="checkbox"/> Appropriateness and/or implementation of reporting checklist (TOP 5 - L3) <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please explain in comments)
Comments	It is not clear whether anonymised transcripts from focus groups will be published as supporting data, although suggested by “comprehensively documented in supporting data”. The list of supporting documents to be made publicly available could be more detailed. It is also not clear whether the “overview of the feedback on the guidance document received in the workshops will be prepared and used by the PG for the revision of INVITES-IN” will be published.

Quick Links: [Objectives](#) | [Experiment](#) | [Analysis](#) | [Transparency](#) | [Ethics](#)

Domain	5. Ethics and interests				
Level of Concern	<input type="checkbox"/> Critical	<input type="checkbox"/> Serious	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate	<input type="checkbox"/> Minor	<input type="checkbox"/> None
Specific Issues	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Informativeness of declarations of interests <input type="checkbox"/> Ethical approval for research with human or animal material or participants <input type="checkbox"/> Other (please explain in comments)				
Comments	Ethical approval has been obtained for the proposed studies. For the sake of transparency, the declarations of interests of individual authors could be more informative and relay more information about professional activities of the authors that could be perceived as a potential conflict of interests.				

Summary section

Summary of compliance issues

What is the impact of the compliance issues you have identified on the publishability of the Working Paper?	Do you agree that it is feasible to overcome the compliance issues?
<input type="checkbox"/> Critical <input type="checkbox"/> Serious <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Moderate <input type="checkbox"/> Minor <input type="checkbox"/> None	<input type="checkbox"/> Strongly disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Neither agree nor disagree <input type="checkbox"/> Somewhat agree <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Strongly agree
Guidance note: Seriousness of the issue is independent of effort required to resolve it. For example, not meeting our requirements for citation standards (TOP 1, level 3) may not require much effort to resolve, but would be a critical issue. Critical and serious issues must be resolved prior to peer-review.	Guidance note: Feasibility is contextual, but in general issues that require additional experimental work or analysis of 3 or more months duration, and/or would result in the study being a different unit of contribution, is less feasible. This is a subjective judgement, provided to inform discussion of how to proceed with the Working Paper.

Summary of manuscript, your overall impression, and suggested course of action

This is a detailed protocol describing the proposed approach to develop a Risk-of-Bias tool specifically aiming at assessing the internal validity of in vitro study. The proposed work is timely and necessary. Overall, the protocol is sound and detailed. The main areas of concern are related to addressing potential bias in the recruitment of focus group/workshop

participants, clarity of the plans for reporting and the conflicts of interest declaration. It should be relatively straightforward to address this concerns to achieve compliance.